

Formative Assessment by Biomedical Engineering Students to Enhance Learning

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Abstract

This article intends to share insights from a pedagogical experience during the academic year 2023-2024 involving 64 students, in the Numerical Methods course in the Biomedical Engineering graduate program at the University of Minho, Portugal. The assessment consists of two summative tests worth 80% of the final grade. Each test comprises a theoretical-practical component and a practical one using MATLAB software. To engage students in the teaching-learning process, prepare them for assessments, and evaluate their progress, two formative tests are proposed before summative test. The formative tests, worth 20% of the final grade, are proposed, solved, and revised by the students. The class is divided into 16 teams of 4 students, and the subject matter into 16 topics. In the first formative test, 8 teams propose an exercise related to one of 8 topics (preferably related to Biomedical Engineering). The remaining 8 teams each solved one of these proposed exercises. The resolution of the exercise is assessed by the proposing team (peer revision). In the second formative test the teams switch their roles for the other 8 topics. The selection of topics among the teams is random, as well as the teams proposing and solving the exercises. The criteria assessment of the team considers: i) proposal of the exercise (creativity, suitability, complexity, real-world application, etc.), ii) assessment of the resolution made by the solving team, iii) exercise solving. A padlet, with a column for team, contains all the proposed exercises, resolutions, and the solving revision. A review of all the course contents is carried out being available online to all students. This experience promotes higher levels of student engagement, performance and satisfaction, promoting their involvement in learning, cooperation, peer revision and the personal construction of knowledge.

Keywords: Formative test; Peer Revision; Problem-Formulation; Problem-solving.

1 Introduction

A truly student-centered approach to education requires assessment practices that are also focused on the student, both working together to promote meaningful learning. Yet, assessment remains one of the least transformed areas of higher education pedagogy. Traditionally, it has emphasized summative, teacher-led evaluation - assessment of learning - that often excludes students from the process. In contrast, student-centered assessment shifts the focus to supporting learning. It includes formative, feedback-driven approaches - assessment for learning - and encourages students to take an active role through assessment as learning, engaging in metacognition, critical thinking, and self-evaluation.

The way students are assessed significantly shapes how they approach their learning and the skills they develop (Brown, 2021, Struyven, Dochy, & Janssens, 2005).

Formative testing plays a crucial role in higher education by enhancing student learning, promoting active engagement, and providing valuable feedback for both students and instructors. Unlike summative assessments, which evaluate overall performance at the end of a learning period, formative tests are designed to monitor progress, identify knowledge gaps, and guide students toward deeper understanding (Black & Wiliam, 1998).

One of the key benefits of formative testing is its ability to reinforce learning through the testing effect, a cognitive phenomenon where retrieving information strengthens memory retention (Roediger & Karpicke, 2006). Regular low-stakes assessments help students consolidate knowledge, making it easier to recall during

high-stakes exams or real-world applications. Additionally, formative assessments encourage self-regulated learning, as students become more aware of their strengths and areas for improvement, allowing them to adjust their study strategies accordingly (Nicol & Macfarlane-Dick, 2006).

From an instructional perspective, formative tests provide educators with actionable insights into student progress, enabling them to tailor teaching methods and address misconceptions before they become deeply ingrained. This approach fosters a more adaptive and student-centered learning environment (Sadler, 1989).

Formative testing is a powerful educational tool that supports continuous learning, self-assessment, and knowledge retention. Its integration into higher education curricula can significantly improve academic performance and overall student development.

A formative test can take different formats, such as quizzes, concept maps, peer assessments, reflective journals, problem-based exercises, oral questioning and discussions. Using a mix of methods keeps students engaged and caters to different learning styles (Shute, 2008). In this experiment, the formative test is created, solved, and assessed by students within a shared, collaborative setting.

The main motivation for this experience is based on several reasons: a) personal passion for pedagogical innovation and curiosity; b) assess the students' ability to apply the studied concepts in the real world (authenticity); c) convey the usefulness of the course within the program; d) monitor student progress and provide continuous feedback during the learning process; e) using AI tool; f) to engage students in peer review practices.

The following sections focus on the formative assessment features (section 2), the methodology adopted in the experiment (section 3), the findings of the experience, based on the analysis of students' perceptions of the approach (section 4), and the conclusions (section 5).

2 Formative assessment

Formative tests aim to track student progress, offer timely feedback, and foster learning development, prioritizing growth over mere performance evaluation. Unlike summative assessments, they emphasize ongoing improvement rather than delivering a final judgment (Black & William, 1998). Formative assessments help identify students' strengths and weaknesses, allowing both learners and educators to adjust their approaches accordingly (Sadler, 1989). They serve as a diagnostic tool, helping instructors tailor their teaching strategies based on student performance. In contrast to summative assessments, which commonly contribute to final grades, formative tests are generally low-stakes and have minimal impact on overall results. Anxiety among students is a significant factor contributing to low academic performance and, in many cases, to dropout. The formative test lowers student anxiety and promotes active engagement with the course in a low-risk learning environment (Nicol & Macfarlane-Dick, 2006).

Formative tests promote metacognition by encouraging students to reflect on their learning strategies. This supports self-regulated learning, where students take an active role in setting goals, monitoring their progress, and adjusting their study methods (Zimmerman, 2002).

Effective formative assessments are conducted regularly throughout the course encouraging students to actively participate in their learning rather than passively receiving information. Interactive activities such as group discussions, think-pair-share, and online polls help maintain motivation and engagement (Prince, 2004).

Providing timely and specific feedback is a core component of formative testing. Feedback should be constructive, guiding students on how to improve their understanding and performance rather than simply indicating right or wrong answers (Hattie & Timperley, 2007).

3 Methodology

The course assessment consists of two summative tests, accounting for 80% of the final grade. To complement these, two formative tests, worth 20% of the final grade, are designed to involve students in both problem formulation and resolution and in peer revision process. The class is divided into 16 teams, each composed of four students. The curriculum content of the course unit is also structured into 16 topics, each formative test cycle covers 8 topics. The process of distributing the topics among the various teams was carried out randomly by means of a draw conducted in the classroom (see 3.1).

The formative assessment process follows these steps for each formative test:

- teams propose exercises related to 8 specific topics within the course syllabus and post them on Padlet in its respective column
- other teams solve the respective exercise and post the resolution below the exercise proposal on Padlet
- the review of the exercise solution is conducted by the team that proposed it and is likewise uploaded to Padlet.

In the second formative test, the teams exchange roles. Specifically, the team that solved the exercises in the first formative test will now propose and review the exercise solution. To make this task easier, the exercise solutions could be handwritten.

The Padlet (Figure 1) is organized into columns, each assigned to a team. Every column is headed by the team's designated number, names and a photo of its four members. A Padlet platform is used to facilitate collaboration, storing all proposed exercises, solutions, and evaluations. The availability of the entire process on Padlet fosters the learning of all students, while also encouraging them to propose engaging exercises. This structured approach fosters student involvement, cooperation, and knowledge construction. The formative test is developed progressively over the course of the semester, in parallel with the delivery of the course content.

Figure 1. Padlet (<https://padlet.com/teresamonteiro/terete/alunos-aprendizagem-ativa-4-valores-rjlldnud435ra57g>)

3.1 Distribution (subjects and roles)

The syllabus of the course unit (Numerical Methods) is structured into 16 subjects (Table 1).

Table 1. Subjects of the course

#	Subject
1	Fundamental Formula of Error
2	1 Nonlinear Equation – Newton’s Method
3	1 Nonlinear Equation – Secant Method
4	Nonlinear System
5	Gauss-Seidel Method
6	Newton Interpolating Polynomial
7	Identify if it is a spline
8	Build Cubic Spline
9	Numerical Integration (data in table)
10	Numerical Integration (function)
11	Least Squares (polynomial model)
12	Least Squares (non-polynomial model)
13	1st Order Differential Equation (initial condition)
14	1st Order System of Differential Equations (initial condition)
15	Higher Order Differential Equation (initial condition)
16	Differential Equation (boundary condition)

Each team takes on two distinct roles: in one formative test, it is responsible for proposing an exercise and evaluating its solution; in the other, it solves an exercise proposed by a different team (Table 2).

Table 2. Allocation of tasks and topics among teams

First formative test			Second Formative test		
Problem setting-group (1..8)	Subject (1..8)	Problem solving-group (9..16)	Problem setting-group (9..16)	Subject (9..16)	Problem solving-group (1..8)
1	1	11	9	11	5
2	3	14	10	12	4
3	6	15	11	13	1
4	8	9	12	15	8
5	2	12	13	16	2
6	7	10	14	9	7
7	4	16	15	14	6
8	5	13	16	10	3

The task of finding a real-world example in which a course concept could be applied was made easier by using the artificial intelligence tool. The proposed exercises focus on topics of great relevance in Biomedical Engineering such as: concentration of drugs in the blood, chemical engineering, administration of morphine in post-operative pain management, meteorology, prosthetics, growth of bacterial cultures, drug diffusion in biological tissues, glucose concentration in a diabetic patient, reactors.

4 Results

The task of proposing the exercise and performing the correction was worth 60% (2.4 points) and took into account the following four assessment criteria: interesting/creative (10%), well formulated (30%), appropriate to the topic (10%) and review (10%). The task of solving the exercise was worth 40% (1.6 points) and was assessed based on two criteria: correctness of the solution (30%) and whether all steps were clearly detailed (10%). For each of the six criteria, a score was assigned on a scale from 1 to 4, with 4 being the highest value.

The results obtained by the teams in this experiment are shown in the Table 3.

Table 3. Team scores (teacher's assessment)

Team	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
Grade(1..4)	4	4	3.2	2.95	4	2	4	3.45	4	4	4	4	4	4	2.8	2.4

Ten of the sixteen teams (62.5%) obtained the maximum score 4 (Table 3). All members of the same team were graded equally. In a future experiment, it is intended that team members will assess their colleagues using a predefined evaluation scheme, in order to ensure a fairer assessment that reflects each member's level of cooperation.

4.1 Students' perceptions

In order to evaluate this pedagogical experience by the students side, a questionnaire was made available on Google Forms with 48 answers in 64 students. The aim was to assess the students' opinions regarding its usefulness, the promotion of authenticity (i.e., application to real-world situations), their level of autonomy, and the use of AI tools. Regarding the usefulness of the pedagogical experience, more than 77% considered it useful or very useful (Figure 2). With regard to establishing connections between the curricular unit's concepts and real-life phenomena (authenticity), the percentage was slightly higher – 81% agreed or strongly agreed (Figure 3). In order to identify the students' level of autonomy, they were asked whether they had requested support from the instructor at any stage – less than 40% did so, which indicates a reasonable degree of autonomy (Figure 4). This autonomy may be explained by the use of the artificial intelligence tool – on this point, more than 77% of the students reported having used it (Figure 5). 71% of the responding students identified the task of proposing the exercise as the most difficult one. In a previous pedagogical experience (Monteiro, Hornink & Vieira, 2021, 2022), students identified the main challenge as finding a real-world phenomenon where a concept from the curricular unit could be applied. The use of the AI tool greatly facilitated this task by helping formulate appropriate questions.

Figure 2. Usefulness in the teaching-learning process (5 – very useful)

Figure 3. Linking theory to real-world practice (authenticity) (5 – very strong link)

Figure 4. Need for teacher support (Sim – Yes; Não – No). Figure 5. Use of artificial intelligence tools

The questionnaire also included an open-ended question where students could express their opinions and possibly suggest improvements. 39 students answered the open-ended questions. Three of these responses are less positive (these students reported that they used Padlet very little during the semester) – more than 92% appreciated this pedagogical experience. Below are some of those comments exactly as they were stated:

- I really liked this form of assessment. It wasn't very complicated and was a different and effective way to consolidate the material taught in class. I wouldn't change anything.
- I liked the activity. I thought that especially the task of proposing exercises helped to better understand the subjects and prepare for the test.

- I liked it and think it should continue.
- I thought it was a good way to deepen my understanding of the subjects since it requires knowing the content in order to solve and propose exercises.
- It was great for testing our skills before each test.

There were also suggestions for improvement, such as, deadlines for the task set in advance, smaller teams, the solutions had to be approved by the teacher before being posted. These suggestions are valuable and will be taken into account in a future similar experiment.

5 Conclusion

This experience allowed students to develop critical thinking skills, promoting teamwork, creativity, authenticity, engagement, using AI tools effectively, and establishing connections with other course units. Preparing students to competently evaluate tasks is fundamental, as such skills will be central to their future professional responsibilities - this competency was fostered through the implementation of peer review.

The student feedback was positive and the teaching and learning environment in which the experience took place was very pleasant.

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